

Deep Learning for Virtual Makeup: Transfer, Recommendation and Removal

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Virtual makeup is becoming a very hot topic in computer vision, machine learning and augmented reality fields. The ability to integrate different methods and techniques from these different fields to make the user experience with cosmetics purchases easier, more interesting and attractive can play a vital role in increasing client satisfaction by allowing consumers to try the product virtually before ordering it online [1]. Client experience in beauty salons can be enriched by makeup transfer from models' faces to customer's faces [2] along with an automatic facial feature analyzer. Recommendations of makeup styles based on facial feature analysis can increase engagement and sales in salons, stores or online [3]; Also, virtual makeup removal can vastly improve the on-site virtual makeup try-on experience in cosmetic stores [4].

2. Aim

To build an advanced e-beauty system for virtual facial makeup that includes: makeup transfer, makeup removal, facial analyzer and makeup recommendation

3. Material and methods

The starting point in our research toward a fully automated e-beauty system for virtual makeup is to collect a big before-after facial makeup database with very detailed manual annotation for all facial features and makeup styles. We apply a deep convolution neural network in a supervised manner to read all facial traits and classify them, then providing the best makeup advice automatically according to the face analyzer results. From the dataset available, a generative adversarial network (GAN) [5] model is trained for both makeup transfer from one face to another and makeup removal at the same time. Also, starting from the annotated dataset, a progressive neural network [6] model is used for makeup recommendation.

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4. Results

The accuracy of the makeup-related facial features classification outperforms current state of the art methods and it succeeds in giving meaningful makeup style recommendations for corrective makeup; The makeup transfer and removal using our proposed GAN model gives high resolution and accurate facial images with a new makeup style for makeup transfer and without makeup for makeup removal. Also, the recommender system using progressive neural network model gives realistic suggestions and high user satisfaction with the recommended styles.

5. Conclusions

The proposed complete and fully automatic e-beauty system that includes facial traits classification, makeup related advice generation, makeup removal and transfer; and makeup recommendation can be deployed in beauty salons, cosmetics stores, and online shopping platforms to increase client satisfaction and enrich the user experience.

6. Keywords

Virtual Makeup, Generative Adversarial Network, eBeauty, Makeup transfer, Makeup Removal.